

Syntheses and spectral studies of new bimetallic Sn^{IV}Al^{III}-μ-oxoisopropoxyacetate and -μ-oxoisopropoxide containing unsymmetrical tin and their β-diketonates

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New bimetallic Sn^{IV}Al^{III}-μ-oxoisopropoxyacetate, BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPrⁱ)₂ [A] and -μ-oxoisopropoxide, BuMeSnO₂Al₂(OPrⁱ)₄ [B] have been synthesized by thermal condensation of BuMeSn(OAc)₂ with aluminium isopropoxide in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio in refluxing xylene. The reaction of [A] with benzoylacetone (bzacH) and thenoyltrifluoroacetone (tfaH) in molar ratios of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 yielded BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPrⁱ)(L) and BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(L)₂. [L = β-diketonate anion]. The reaction of [B] with bzacH and tfaH in molar ratios 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 yielded complexes of the types BuMeSnO₂Al₂(OPrⁱ)₃(L) and BuMeSnO₂Al₂(OPrⁱ)₂(L)₂. These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses and spectral studies (IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, ¹¹⁹Sn NMR and ²⁷Al NMR).

Mixed metal oxides, especially those of transition metals are well known for their interesting properties which have led to key applications in such fields as solid state physics and heterogeneous catalyst¹. Teyssie *et al.*² explored the possibility to synthesize polynuclear complexes containing M-O-M' units, which at the same time would be soluble in organic media and still mimic some of the important properties of metal oxide in heterogeneous system. These substances enjoying combined properties due to the presence of different metals could be of great interest in modeling the synergic effect existing between the oxo-bridged metals. Such interactions usually result in extremely interesting delocalization and magnetic exchanges^{3,4}. These compounds could also represent a good model for biologically important hemerythrin⁵ and hemeprotein⁶ systems.

Interest in β-diketonate derivatives arise due to their applications in such diverse areas as gas chromatography, polymer chemistry, laser technology, solvent extraction and shift reagent in NMR spectroscopy⁷.

Results and discussion

BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPrⁱ)₂ and BuMeSnO₂Al₂(OPrⁱ)₄ have been prepared by refluxing butylmethyltin diacetate and aluminium isopropoxide in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios respectively in xylene. The reaction can be depicted as follows :

The above reaction involves stepwise replacement of the acetyl groups, as was confirmed by determining the isopropyl acetate liberated during the progress of the reaction. Compounds [A] and [B] were yellow solid, highly susceptible to hydrolysis and soluble in common organic solvents.

The reaction of [A] and [B] with β-diketones may be represented as follows :

(where n = 1–2 and L = bzac or tfa)

The isopropanol liberated in the reaction was collected azeotropically as binary azeotrope of isopropanol-benzene and was estimated oxidimetrically.

The complexes thus obtained were pale yellow solid, soluble in benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, DMSO and hexane, susceptible to hydrolysis and tend to decompose on heating. The fact that further isopropoxy groups were not displaced even with an excess of ligand and increase in refluxing time indicate that two types of isopropoxy groups were present i.e. bridging and terminal. Bridging isopropoxy groups were not usually displaced.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of [A] and [B] exhibited bands at ~ 1160 and $\sim 1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C-O} + \text{OPr}^i)$ terminal and $\nu(\text{C-O} + \text{OPr}^i)$ bridging groups, respectively. A band appearing at $\sim 1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{C-O})$ of the acetyl groups⁸, in the IR spectrum of [A] was found to be absent in [B] suggesting the complete replacement of acetyl groups. The band appearing at $\sim 950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was due to the bridging isopropoxy groups⁹. A number of band observed in the region $700\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were due to metal-oxygen bond. In the IR spectra of β -diketonates, the $\nu(\text{O-H})$ band occurring in the region of $3100\text{--}2700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappeared completely, thus indicating deprotonation of the β -diketone. The band observed between $1620\text{--}1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{C-O})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{C-O})$ of acetate and β -diketone. A band observed at $\sim 1520\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was assigned to the $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{C-C})$ vibration of the β -diketone moiety. The non shifting of the $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{C-C})$ band observed in the β -diketone confirmed that both carbonyl groups were coordinating. The band appearing at ~ 1200 and 1080 cm^{-1} were due to $\nu(\text{C-S})$ and $\nu(\text{C-F})$, respectively.

¹H NMR spectra :

¹H NMR spectra of β -diketones displayed a signal at ~ 13 due to enolic OH which was absent in the derivatives of [A] and [B], suggesting that replacement of protons took place in the enolic form. A broad peak, centered at $\delta 2.1$ in the complexes of [A] was due to mixing of methyl proton of acetate and benzoylacetate. A broad overlapping multiplet centered at $\delta \sim 1.0$ in the derivatives was due to the mixing of methyl protons of the bridging and terminal isopropoxy groups along with the protons of butyl and methyl groups. A multiplet centered at $\delta 4.0$ in some complexes was due to methine protons of the isopropoxy groups. The proton integration area of methine protons of the isopropoxy groups to methyl of acetate was consistent with the replacement of one acetyl group only. A singlet at $\delta 6.4$ was assignable to methine protons of the ligand moiety. The peaks observed in the region $\delta 7.9\text{--}7.1$ were assigned to the phenyl and thenoyl ring protons of the ligands.

¹³C NMR spectra :

¹³C NMR spectra of [A] and [B] displayed two promi-

nent peaks at $\delta 26.2$ and 27.3 due to methyl carbons of terminal and intermolecularly bridged isopropoxy moieties. Two signals at $\delta 62.9$ and 63.8 were assigned to two different types of methine carbons of the isopropoxy groups¹⁰. The spectrum of [B] exhibited two additional peaks at $\delta 27.9$ and 64.3 due to methyl and methine carbons of intramolecularly bridged isopropoxy moiety. No isopropoxy peaks were observed in the 1 : 2 derivatives of [A], thus suggesting the complete substitution of the isopropoxy groups by β -diketone. The signals observed in the range of $\delta 193.8\text{--}183.0$ and $\delta 117.8$ were due to carbonyl carbon and $-\text{CF}_3$ groups, respectively. A sharp singlet observed at $\delta 96.8\text{--}93.4$ was due to methine carbon of the ligand moiety. Phenyl and thenoyl ring carbons were observed in the range $\delta 145.7\text{--}127.1$. The butyl and methyl carbons appeared at their usual positions¹¹.

²⁷Al NMR spectra :

²⁷Al NMR spectrum of [A] exhibited a broad signal in the range of $\delta 63.6\text{--}40.0$ that was probably due to an equilibrium between tetra- and penta-coordinated Al environment in the solution¹². ²⁷Al NMR spectrum of [B] displayed a signal at $\delta 71.7$ that could be attributed to the tetrahedral environment about the Al atom. ²⁷Al NMR spectra of bzac and tfa derivatives of [A] displayed a signals at $\delta 1.8$ and 2.2 , respectively, that could be ascribed to the hexacoordinated Al atom. ²⁷Al NMR spectra of bzac and tfa derivatives of [B] produced the signals at $\delta \sim 66$, $\delta 1.8$ and $\delta \sim 67$, $\delta 6.1$, respectively that could be assigned to the tetrahedral and octahedral environment about the Al atom.

¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra :

¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectrum of [A] displayed a sharp signal at $\delta 78.5$ and a broad peak at $\delta \sim 144.5$ that was probably due to an equilibrium between tetra- and penta-coordinated Sn environment in the solution¹³. ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra of [B] and 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 derivatives of [A] and [B] produced signal at $\delta \sim 79$ which were assignable to tetra-coordinated Sn environment.

Conclusion :

On the basis of above investigations, the tentative structures (Figs. 1–6) have been assigned to these complexes.

Experimental

All manipulations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere in vacuum line by using Schlenk techniques. Aluminium isopropoxide was prepared by reported method¹⁴. Metal and isopropoxy determinations were carried out as described elsewhere^{15,16}. BuMeSnCl₂ was prepared by reported method¹⁷. IR spectra (4000–

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

were recorded on a Bruker-300, 300 MHz instrument with TMS, $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and tetramethyltin as internal standards respectively, at RSIC, Chandigarh.

Synthesis of $\text{BuMeSn}(\text{OAc})_2$:

To a solution of butylmethyltin dichloride (6.36 g, 24.32 mmol) in ~40 ml of benzene was added (7.98 g, 97.26 mmol) of sodium acetate. The resulting solution was further refluxed for 8 h and then filtered. The filtrate was evaporated

200 cm^{-1}) were recorded as thin films on CsI plates on Perkin-Elmer 842 and 632 Grating spectrophotometer.

^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R-32, 90 MHz spectrometer. ^{13}C , ^{27}Al and ^{119}Sn NMR spectra

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

and the resulting product was distilled under reduced pressure.

Synthesis of $BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPr^i)_2$:

$BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPr^i)_2$ was prepared by refluxing aluminium isopropoxide (1.10 g, 5.39 mmol) and

Fig. 6

butylmethyltin diacetate (1.67 g, 5.39 mmol) in xylene for 6 h on a fractionating column. The isopropyl acetate so formed was fractionated continuously from 80 to 139°. The excess of xylene was distilled off to give a light yellow solid. The product was then recrystallised in benzene to give light yellow glassy solid.

Synthesis of $BuMeSnO_2Al_2(OPr^i)_4$:

$BuMeSnO_2Al_2(OPr^i)_4$ was prepared by refluxing butylmethyltin diacetate (3.22 g, 10.4 mmol) and aluminium isopropoxide (4.25 g, 20.82 mmol) in xylene for nearly 8 h on a fractionating column. The isopropyl acetate formed in the reaction was fractionated continuously from 80° to boiling xylene (139°). The reaction was further continued at this temperature for 1 h to ensure its completion. The excess of xylene was distilled off under reduced pressure at 40°/1 mm Hg, leaving behind yellow solid. The product was redissolved in benzene. Slow evaporation of benzene furnished pale yellow glassy solid.

Reaction of $BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPr^i)_2$ with benzoylacetone in 1 : 1 molar ratio :

Benzoylacetone (0.24 g, 1.46 mmol) was added to a clear solution of $BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPr^i)_2$ (0.60 g, 1.46 mmol) in ~50 ml benzene. The reaction contents were refluxed for about 2 h. The liberated isopropanol was collected at 72–78° as binary azeotrope of isopropanol-benzene. The completion of the reaction was checked by oxidimetric method. The excess of solvent was removed under reduced

Table 1. β-Diketonates of BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPrⁱ)₂ and BuMeSnO₂Al₂(OPrⁱ)₄

Compd. g (mmol)	Ligand g (mmol)	Molar ratio	Refluxing time	Product g (%)	Analysis(%) : Found (Calcd.)		
					Pr ⁱ O(g)	Sn	Al
BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPr ⁱ) ₂ 0.60 (1.46)	Hbzac 0.24 (1.46)	1 : 1	2	BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPr ⁱ)(bzac) 0.51 (66)	0.08 (0.08)	22.8 (23.1)	4.9 (5.3)
BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPr ⁱ) ₂ 0.53 (1.30)	Hbzac 0.42 (2.60)	1 : 2	3	BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(bzac) ₂ 0.58 (70)	0.14 (0.15)	18.8 (19.3)	3.9 (4.4)
BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPr ⁱ) ₂ 0.59 (1.42)	Htfa 0.32 (1.42)	1 : 1	2	BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPr ⁱ)(tfa) 0.57 (69)	0.08 (0.08)	20.2 (20.7)	4.4 (4.7)
BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPr ⁱ) ₂ 0.58 (1.42)	Htfa 0.63 (2.83)	1 : 2	3	BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(tfa) ₂ 0.69 (67)	0.16 (0.17)	15.8 (16.1)	3.4 (3.7)
BuMeSnO ₂ Al ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₄ 0.93 (1.82)	Hbzac 0.29 (1.82)	1 : 1	2	BuMeSnO ₂ Al ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₃ (bzac) 0.79 (69)	0.10 (0.10)	18.9 (19.3)	8.5 (8.8)
BuMeSnO ₂ Al ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₄ 1.03 (2.01)	Hbzac 0.65 (4.02)	1 : 2	3	BuMeSnO ₂ Al ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₂ (bzac) ₂ 1.04 (69)	0.11 (0.12)	16.2 (16.6)	7.2 (7.5)
BuMeSnO ₂ Al ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₄ 0.56 (1.10)	Htfa 0.24 (1.10)	1 : 1	2	BuMeSnO ₂ Al ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₃ (tfa) 0.52 (70)	0.06 (0.06)	17.2 (17.6)	7.8 (8.0)
BuMeSnO ₂ Al ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₄ 0.62 (1.20)	Htfa 0.54 (2.41)	1 : 2	3	BuMeSnO ₂ Al ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₂ (tfa) ₂ 0.68 (67)	0.14 (0.14)	13.9 (14.2)	6.2 (6.5)

pressure (40°/1 mm Hg) that produced a pale yellow solid.

Attempts were also made to sublime this compound under reduced pressure but the compound decomposes above 180° at 0.01 mm Hg. A similar procedure was used for the other reaction of β-diketones with BuMeSn(OAc)OAl(OPrⁱ)₂ and BuMeSnO₂Al₂(OPrⁱ)₄ in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios. Details are given in Table 1 along with the analytical data.

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